

Early Daoist text—Commands and Admonitions for the Families of the Great Dao (Dadaojia lingjie 大道家令戒)

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Entry tags: Yellow and Yangzi Rivers Region, Wei-Jin text, Daoism, Daoist text, Text, Religious Group, Early Chinese Traditions, Canonical texts

This entry introduces one of earliest Daoist texts, the Commands and Admonitions for the Families of the Great Dao (Dadaojia lingjie 大道家令戒). What the text upholds and criticizes, with the historical and social background of its composition, reflect perceived problems regarding certain aspects of contemporaneous practice in the face of community diaspora, from Hanzhong 漢中, a region of modern southeastern Shaanxi 陝西 and northeastern Sichuan 四川 provinces to the Wei 魏 kingdom (220–266). The Admonitions, which is deemed to be written in 255 CE, is the main part of a larger compendium known as the Commandments of the Celestial Master from the One and Orthodox Canon (Zhengyi fawen tianshi jiaojie kejing 正一法文天師教戒科經). This corpus contains the doctrines of the Celestial Master Movement (Tianshi dao 天師道), often regarded as the earliest Daoist community. Followers believe that the Celestial Masters was founded upon the revelations of Laozi 老子, a Covenant with the Powers that was both correct and unique in the world (Zhengyi mengwei 正一盟威) to Zhang Ling 張陵 (fl. 142 CE), the First Celestial Master, in the Swan-Call Mountain. So, Daode jing 道德經 that was said to be a work by Laozi was adopted as the primary text for believers' physical and moral cultivation. The Celestial Masters' base at the time was established in Hanzhong, as a theocratic state which was supported by twenty-four parishes (zhi 治), each of which was led by a libationer (jijiu 祭酒). However, after its leader, the Third Celestial Master Zhang Lu's 張魯 (d. 216?) surrendered to the ruler of Wei, Cao Cao 曹操 (155–220), the community was forcibly dispersed. One group of followers was moved to Chang'an 長安, modern Xi'an 西安 and its surrounding areas, and the other group was moved to Luoyang 洛陽 and Ye 鄴 where is near modern Handan 邯鄲. Luoyang and Ye are not far, about 364 kilometers apart. As part of the surrender, Zhang Lu, was granted the title "General Who Subdues the South" (Zhennan jiangjun 鎮南將軍) and relocated to Cao Cao's Wei kingdom. Therefore, without a central authority, the power of the previous theocratic state in Hanzhong was somewhat thawed, leading to the system of twenty-four parishes being undermined. As a result, the theocratic state destabilized and the concern over the heterodox practices increasingly grew. The Admonitions was composed in order to rectify what was viewed as a decline in rules and corruption of doctrines. Given that it was written in the first person, some scholars have considered that the author would be Zhang Lu himself. However, such attribution seems dubious as Zhang Lu likely died before the Admonitions was written. Nonetheless, it is possible that the message was pronounced by a medium, perhaps one of Zhang Lu's sons, in the voice of Zhang Lu that explains why the first person pronoun was adopted by the text. This speculation was first made by the Chinese scholar, Hu Shi 胡適 (1891–1962) and then affirmed by Daoist scholars like Stephen R. Bokenkamp and Terry F. Kleeman. The text of the Admonitions describes what changes brought to the Celestial Masters after it relocated throughout the Wei kingdom and how to rectify the "incorrect practices" prevalent among the faithful. For instance, the Admonitions determined that since the fifth year of Grand Harmony 太和 reign period (231 CE), those self-appointed libationers, whose promotions were not emanated from the "true pneuma", violated the old regulations regarding the selection and appointment. The Admonitions cautioned that from the day of the release of the Admonitions, self-promotion was absolutely prohibited. Although the Admonitions was a criticism directed at the problems of the Celestial Masters, intriguingly, it ostensibly eulogized the governance of the Wei and propagated the Confucian virtue that make it different from previous Daoist texts. It claimed that "the Wei, receiving [the mandate of] Heaven, drives away and exterminates [the evils]." So, the changes of the rhetoric can be seen in Admonitions when the leaders of the Celestial Master were assimilated into the

authority. Despite little is know about the fate of the Celestial Masters once it left from Hanzhong, based on the Admonitions, a general picture concerning dramatic changes happened to the central organization, the religious specialists and the believers after Hanzhong diaspora can be sketched out.

Date Range: 200 CE - 500 CE

Region: Hanzhong 漢中 movement to the North and the Central Plain

Region tags: China, East Asia

Hanzhong 漢中 (modern Hanzhong) is the old base of the Celestial Master, after Zhang Lu's 張魯 surrender to Cao Cao 曹操, they were moved to Chang'an 長安 (modern Xi'an 西安), Luoyang 洛陽 (modern Luoyang) and Ye 鄴 (modern Handan 邯鄲)

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Nickerson, Peter. "Taoism and Medium Cults." In *The Encyclopedia of Taoism*, vol. II, edited by Fabrizio Pregadio, 156–159. Abingdon: Routledge, 2017.
- Source 2: Li, Gang 李剛. "Wei Jin Nanchao Zhengyidao shenxue sixiang pouxi—yi Zhengyi fawen tianshi jiaojie kejing, Santian neijie jing weili." 魏晉南朝正一道神學思想剖析—以《正一法文天師教戒科經》《三天內解經》為例 *Zongjiaoxue yanjiu* 宗教學研究 4 (2017): 13–21.
- Source 3: Jiang, Sheng 姜生. "Cao Cao yu yuanshi daojiao" 曹操與原始道教 *Lishi yanjiu* 歷史研究 1 (2011): 4–24.
- Source 1: Wu, Chengquan 伍成泉. "Hanmo weijin nanbeichao daojiao jielü guifan yanjiu." 漢末魏晉南北朝道教戒律規範研究 PhD diss. Central China Normal University 華中師範大學, 2005. See esp. chap. 2, "Weijin nanbeichao daojiao jielü guifan de jingdian wenxian." 魏晉南北朝道教戒律規範的經典文獻
- Source 2: Tang, Changru 唐長孺. "Weijin qijian beifang tianshidao de chuanbo." 魏晉期間北方天師道的傳播 In *Weijin nanbeichao shilun shiyi* 魏晉南北朝史論拾遺, 218–232. Beijing: Zhonghua shuju, 1983.
- Source 3: Goodman, Howard L. "Celestial-Master Taoism and the Founding of the Ts'ao-Wei Dynasty: The Li Fu Document." *Asia Major* 7, no. 1 (1994): 5–33.
- Source 1: Robinet, Isabelle. "The Celestial Masters." In *Taoism: Growth of a Religion*, translated by Phyllis Brooks, 53–77. Stanford: Stanford University Press, 1997.
- Source 2: Yoshikawa, Tadao 吉川忠夫. 六朝精神史研究. 京都: 同朋舍, 1984. See esp. chap. 2, "真人と革命."
- Source 3: Seidel, Anna. "Imperial Treasures and Taoist Sacraments: Taoist Roots in the Apocrypha." In *Tantric and Taoist Studies: In Honor of R.A. Stein*, vol. 2, edited by Michael Strickmann, 291–371. Brussels: Institut Belge des Hautes Etudes Chinoises, 1983.
- Source 1: Chan, Timothy Wai Keung. "Ruan Ji on Apocalypse." In *Considering the End: Mortality in early Medieval Chinese Poetic Representation*, 65–96. Leiden: Brill, 2012.
- Source 2: Wang, Jing 王璟. "Zhengyi fawen tianshi jiaojie kejing." 《正一法文天師教戒科經》成書年代考辨

Chengda zhongwen xuebao 成大中文學報 46 (2014): 69–98.

- Source 3: Kleeman, Terry F. "Daoism in the Third Century." In *Purposes, Means and Convictions in Daoism*, edited by Florian C. Reiter, 11–28. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz, 2007.
- Source 1: Kleeman, Terry F. *Celestial Masters: History and Ritual in Early Daoist Communities*. Cambridge and London: Harvard University Press, 2016.
- Source 2: Liu, Yi 劉屹. "Lun Dongjin nanchao jiangdong tianshidao de lishi yuanyuan—Yi Dadao xinyang wei zhongxin." 論東晉南朝江東天師道的歷史淵源—以大道信仰為中心 *Wenshi 文史* 122 (2018): 97–116.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=snYAgWumsIU>
- Source 1 Description: This video (Chinese) briefly introduces the historical background and political environment of the building of the theocratic state by Zhang Lu in Hanzhong.
- Source 2 URL: http://blog.sina.com.cn/s/blog_7e84ef460102y32c.html
- Source 2 Description: This blog (Chinese) explains why after Zhang Lu surrendered to Cao Cao, Cao Cao granted titles and fiefs to Zhang Lu and his sons.
- Source 3 URL: [http://wikipedia.us.nina.az/wiki/Zhang_Lu_\(Han_dynasty\)](http://wikipedia.us.nina.az/wiki/Zhang_Lu_(Han_dynasty))
- Source 3 Description: This provides supplementary information about Zhang Lu's family lineage.
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.163.com/dy/article/G1789PL60543H7L0.html>
- Source 1 Description: This online article (Chinese) explains a possible reason why Cao Cao could win the battle with Zhang Wei 張衛 (fl. 3th c.) who was Zhang Lu's younger brother which victory eventually led to Zhang Lu's surrender.
- Source 2 URL: https://www.hmoob.in/wiki/Celestial_Masters
- Source 2 Description: This introduces the brief history of the way of the Celestial Masters.
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.casterio.com/profile/terry-kleeman>
- Source 3 Description: This is an interview with Professor Terry Kleeman who authored, *Celestial Masters: History and Ritual in Early Daoist Communities*, in 2016, which is a monograph on the Celestial Masters.

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <http://taolibrary.com/category/category109/c1090497.htm?pageno=317>
- Source 1 Description: Dadaojia lingjie is the part 2 of Zhengyi fawen tianshi jiaojie kejing 正一法文天師教戒科經. This is the full corpus including Tianshi jiao 天師教, Yangping zhi 陽平治 and Tianshi wuyan qian sanshi 天師五言牽三詩.
- Source 2 URL: <http://taolibrary.com/category/category109/c1090555.htm?pageno=169>
- Source 2 Description: This is Xiang'er's Commentary on Daode jing (Laozi Daode jing Xiang'er zhu 老子道德經想爾註), attributed to the founder of the Celestial Masters, Zhang ling. Dadaojia lingjie represents some different ideas from Laozi Daodejing Xiang'er zhu.
- Source 3 URL: <http://taolibrary.com/category/category96/c960142.htm#>

– Source 3 Description: There are biographies of Zhang Lu's sons included in the Comprehensive Mirror of True Transcendents Who Embodied the Dao of All Ages (Lidai zhenxian tidao tongjian 歷代真仙體道通鑒).

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

↳ Inked

– with Ink

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 400 CE

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

↳ Specify type of paper

– Specify: The early paper was crude and coarse, made of either hemp fibers or silk rags, but according to Denis Twitchett's *Printing and Publishing in Medieval China*, by the fourth century, it had replaced the old writing materials like the wood or bamboo slip or the silk scroll. But some scholars like Xin Deyong 辛德勇 suggests that the extensive use of paper as a writing material started from the Northern and Southern dynasties (420-589).

– Bamboo

Notes: Although most scholars like Rao Zongyi 饒宗頤, Ofuchi Ninji 大淵忍爾 and Stephen Bokenkamp, agree that Dadaojia lingjie was written during the Wei (220-266), some scholars hold different opinions, such as Tang Yongtong 湯用彤 who assumes that it was written by the Northern Wei Daoist master, Kou Qianzhi 寇謙之 (365-448); Tang Changru 唐長孺 and Ren Jiyu 任繼愈 contend that it was written in the early period of the Northern Wei (386-534), while Kobayashi Masayoshi 小林正美 and Liu Yi 劉屹 consider that it was written during the Southern Song (420-479). So, the dating of Dadaojia lingjie is still under discussion. However, given the fact that the circulating writing materials of that period were bamboo and wood slips, silk scrolls, and also paper, the text probably was written on them.

– Silk

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: The authorship is not identified. Some scholars suggest that the text was pronounced and written down by a spiritual medium in the voice of Zhang Lu or Zhang Ling. So, if the medium knew that the spirits would descend at certain time, some physical or ritual preparation might be involved.

Notes: According to Dadaojia lingjie, the text was released on the seventh day of the first month which day is significant because it is reserved for the first of the three yearly assemblies of the Celestial Masters. So, Stephen Bokenkamp suggests that the text would have been read to the communities of the faithful at that time. If that is true, it is more likely that the seance is scheduled. Alan Elliott assumes that the spiritual medium has little choice as to when and where he will become possessed, but the spiritual medium could call down the "shen" 神 by means of invocation at certain places such as spirit-medium temple. Therefore, the material might be modified before the writing if they knew that the "shen" would descend.

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

— Other [specify]: It is not certain. If Dadaojia lingjie was a declaration of the ascended Zhang Lu or Zhang Ling, it was transmitted orally, so it likely was not modified before it was written down. It should be spontaneous.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

— I don't know

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

— I don't know

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

— I don't know

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

— Field doesn't know

Notes: The text was written after the Celestial Masters were moved to the Wei kingdom ruled by the Cao family, and the leaders of the Celestial Masters, Zhang Lu and his sons were enfeoffed. In addition to that, in the text, the governance of the Wei was praised, so it is possible that the writing of the text was supported by the authority but whether it was funded by the polity is not certain.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

— No

Notes: It is about admonitions about the organization of Daoist church and libationers's promotion. So, the text is not the kind of revealing theological ideas.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: However, there are some uncommon vocabularies that seem exclusive to Dadaojia lingjie, such as "breaking through the pneumas" (jueqi 決氣). Stephen Bokenkamp and Terry Kleeman both suggest that the word is related to an officer of twenty-four parishes, the director of determinations (lingjue 領決) who is responsible for determining the truth of mediumistic pronouncements, even though the word, "jueqi" seems not to appear in other texts.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The written time of the text is not certain. But some scholars attribute the text to Zhang Lu. Zhang Lu died in the second year after relocating to the Wei kingdom. So, the audience should be those followers of the Celestial Masters who newly moved to the Wei. According to the Book of Wei (Weishu 魏書), hundreds of thousands of households (hu 戶, 1 hu is approximately equal to 5.93 people), around 700000 to 1 million people, with Zhang Lu from the theocratic state of Hanzhong were moved to the North by Cao Cao. They were the possible audience.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– I don't know

Notes: Before Hanzhong movements, the Celestial Masters was a theocratic state in which the policy of "guiding the households and educating the populace" 領戶化民 was enacted, which means that the libationers were responsible for educating the populace of their own parishes. Newcomers, like newborn babies or immigrants from other parishes, needed to register for their new parish and to follow their new libationer. Therefore, a sort of competition between parishes and libationers existed. After one received 150-general-register (yibaiwushi jiangjun lu 一百五十將軍籙), one was considered as being fully ordained and able to act as an itinerant priest to teach and convert people. According to the rules of promotion in Protocol for the External Registers (Zhengyi fawen taishang wailu yi 正一法文太上外籙儀), "if they convert three people, this is a Merit; three Merits constitute an Endeavor; three Endeavors constitute an Award. Those with an Award possess virtue and can be appointed to an Inner, Outer, or Stellar Parish. They receive these according to the prescribed order." 化得三人為一功，三功為一勤，三勤為一勳。勳者有德，仍得署治內，外，星宿，隨次受之。 (Translation see Kleeman, "Authority and Discipline in the Early Daoist Church", 50). So, these itinerant Daoist priests would actively convert and recruit new followers to get promotions in the Daoist church, but those established libationers who directed fixed parishes also wanted to secure old followers and to entice new followers to obtain more tithes that followers submitted to maintain the parish. So, in this sense, all libationers would eagerly recruit new members. In addition, the epigraphical evidence of the sixth-century shows that the Daoist communities, especially those in the northwestern region, represent some Buddho-Daoist characteristics. Followers there regarded these two faiths as compatible. Stephen Bokenkamp's article about Yao Boduo's 姚伯多 stele of 496 CE, a Buddho-Daoist hybrid stele shows that Lingbao 靈寶 scriptures allowed that Buddhas and bodhisattvas could still be venerated as long as it was understood that they were but later emanations of the Dao of Lingbao. For Lingbao tradition, being tolerant to Buddhism is a way to convert Buddhists, although it is not certain whether the Celestial Masters did the same conversion or not.

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but it happened later, in the fifth century. Kou Qianzhi 寇謙之 (365-448) was a renowned reformist of the Celestial Masters who removed the outdated and false methods proposed by the contemporary Daoist priests, such as some "fake" arts like the bed-chamber (fangzhong shu 房中術) which to him, were not the true methods of "yellow-red" transmitted by Celestial Master Zhang Ling. Kou Qianzhi advocated the arts of transcendence, such as pulling and guiding and grain-avoiding, in addition to that, he emphasized the importance of fasting. The Scripture of the Intoned Precepts of Lord Lao (Laojun yinsong jiejing 老君音誦誡經) by Kou Qianzhi also added new precepts to regulate practitioners of the Celestial Masters.

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– I don't know

Notes: Dunhuang Daoist Canon (Dunhuang daoze 敦煌道藏) seems to not include a different version of this text.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: It is a part of the Daoist corpus, Commandments of the Celestial Master from the One and Orthodox Canon (Zhengyi fawen tianshi jiaojie kejing 正一法文天師教戒科經).

Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Notes: The text belongs to the "Precept and Regulation" of the collection.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: No

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The incorrect practice the text criticized was self-promotion because the promotion was not from the "true pneuma". In other words, libationers' promotions were supposed to be given by the "true pneuma"---the Celestial Master 天師, which is an orthodox way to get promoted in the hierarchy of the Daoist church. So, a sort of lineage emanated from the "true pneuma"--the Celestial Master 天師 formed.

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, Celestial Masters 天師 (True Pneuma) generally designate the First Celestial Master Zhang Ling, the Second Celestial Master Zhang Heng 張衡 (?-179) who is the son of Zhang Ling and the Third Celestial Master Zhang Lu who is the son of Zhang Heng. So, the authority of the Celestial Masters was consisted of Zhang family members.

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– No

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Blood or Marriage relations

Notes: Three Celestial Masters were related by blood. Libationers of twenty-four parishes should be elected by them. However, based on this text, after three Celestial Masters passed away, it seems that the election and promotion should be done by their spirits.

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– I don't know

Notes: The text criticizes those practitioners, especially those self-appointed libationers who discarded old rules on promotion but whether it became a formal legal code for a period of time is not certain. In any rate, the system of twenty-four parishes eventually collapsed after the base was relocated to the

Wei kingdom.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentions "seed people of latter-day generation" 後世種民.

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– I don't know

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Some scholars suggest that the text was pronounced by a spiritual medium in the voice of ascended Zhang Lu. If that is the case, the supernatural being was involved.

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

Notes: The text was written in the first person, such as "from now on, I will hide myself from the world and entrust you upon the Wei" 從今吾避世，以汝付魏。

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– I don't know

Notes: The divine persona in this revelation seems not very suitable to the category of "sky deity". If the divine was Zhang Lu as most scholars suggested, even though he is the representative of "true pneuma", he is not exactly a deity in the sky as it may be related to other "sky deities" found across this database.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

Notes: The king himself is not the high god but the great dao is closely associated with the king. For instance, "[the great dao] is the teacher of the king from generation to generation" 世世為帝王師. If the state suffers the disasters, that is because the king does not listen to his "teacher".

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– Yes

Notes: If in this text, elites refer to libationers, they are a kin relation to the supreme high god because they were emanated from "the great dao".

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– I don't know

Notes: The text was written to criticize the libationers who violated the old rules and ask them to get back on right track, by threatening "if one goes against my rules again, please do not blame [me] if one is hurted" 復違吾，中傷勿怨。 However, for the chaos caused by wars, this text implies that the process of going declined from prosperity is natural. For instance, it states "expecting the dawn, one has to experience the dusk first; expecting the great peace, one has to experience the chaos first" 欲朝當先暮，欲太平當先亂。 What "the great dao" will do is to bestow and spread the correct dao.

However, whether one can be saved by the dao is to depend on oneself, because "one bears the dao in mind, then the dao will consider the one; while one does not think of the dao, then the dao will not consider the one." 子念道，道念子；子不念道，道不念子也。 So, the great dao will certainly protect the people who follow the dao and punish the people who violate the rules set up by him.

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: The great dao always finds a representative to help him spread the correct dao.

Notes: For Daoism, the Dao is not only conceived as an anthropomorphic concept of "supreme high god", but also, it more often refers to the ontological stage. According to the Xiang'er Commentary to the Laozi 老子想尔註, attributed to Zhang Lu 張魯, it reads as follows, "when the one scatters, it becomes qi; when the one gets together, it becomes the Lord Lao of the Grand Ultimate" 一散形為氣，聚形為太上老君, the one is the dao which can become either qi or the Lord Lao of the Grand Ultimate. In addition, the great dao always finds a representative to help him spread the correct dao. The dao depicted in this text with anthropomorphic attributes can be addressed in the following questions. The great dao exists everlastingly. In different time periods, the great dao will bestow the correct dao upon different correct people, for example, first, in the end of Eastern Zhou (770-256), Gan Ji 干吉 was the chosen person who received the dao and the Book of Great Peace, with Green Headings (Taiping qinglingshu 太平清領書); then, Laozi 老子 (571-471) was selected to receive the dao and he wrote a text in five thousand words that is Daode jing 道德經 and he gave the text to Yinxi 尹喜 in the western pass to spread it; on the first day of the fifth month of the first year of Han'an 漢安 reign period (142CE), in Chishi city 赤石城 of Linqiong prefecture 臨邛縣 of Shu county 蜀郡, Zhang Daoling 張道陵 (34-156) was selected as the first Celestial Master to establish twenty-four parishes and spread the qi of xuan 玄 and yuan 元 and shi 始 that means the dao.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

Notes: As the text states, "from the heaven, the earth and below, all lives are generated and eliminated by the dao" 自天地以下, 皆道所生殺也, so it is the dao who creates the world.

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– I don't know

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– I don't know

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– I don't know

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– I don't know

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– I don't know

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: The texts states that "The three eras—Xia, Shang, and Zhou—saw a turn to desire for worldly profit. Then the Inaugural Thearch of the Qin and the Five Hegemons attacked and injured one another and banditry arose. Millions died—more than can be counted. All of this occurred through loss of faith with the Dao." 夏商周三代，轉見世利。秦始皇五霸，更相剋害。有賊死者，萬億不可勝數。皆由不信其道。 Translation see: Stephen R. Bokenkamp, *Early Daoist Scriptures* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1997), 167.

↳ Can reward
— Yes

↳ Can punish
— Yes

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
— No

↳ Exhibits positive emotion
— Yes

Notes: The great dao shows a positive emotion by arguing that if one concentrates on practicing good actions, one can be the "seed people" saved and enjoy great peace in the future. The text states: "all of our households should transform one another through loyalty and filiality, so that fathers are magnanimous and sons filial, husbands faithful and wives chaste, elder brothers respectful and the younger obedient. Mornings and evenings you should practice 'clarity and stillness.' Root out all covetousness, abandon the pursuit of personal profit, and rid yourself of desire.....Abandon all of your past evil pursuits. Those who, from today on, practice good actions will find that disaster and disease melt away from them, and will become seed people of the later age." 但當戶戶自相化以忠孝，父慈子孝，夫信婦貞，兄敬弟順，朝暮清淨，斷絕貪心，棄利去慾.....棄往日之惡，從今日之善行，災消無病，得為後世種民. Translation please see: Stephen R. Bokenkamp, *Early Daoist Scripture* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1997), 181.

↳ Exhibits negative emotion
— Yes

Notes: The great dao criticizes many vulgar people whose actions go against the dao. "You vulgar people are truly comical: When you do some small good deed, you always want others to know of it, and when you differ by so much as a grain of rice from others, you expect to be considered worthy. These are the sorts of benefit derived from what is not the Dao." 俗人輩，汝曹狀可笑也。纔有小善，欲使人知之，纔有粉米之異，欲使人賢之。此皆犯禁矣. Translation please see: Stephen R. Bokenkamp, *Early Daoist Scripture* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1997), 182-183.

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

– Specify: The great dao only transmits the dao to the right person and makes the person be his representative to assist the world and spread the correct dao. The great dao does not spread the dao himself. It usually happens when the world collapses.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life

– No

↳ In dreams

– I don't know

↳ In trance possession

– I don't know

↳ Through divination practices

– I don't know

↳ Only through religious specialists

– I don't know

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

Notes: Yes, it is said that the one who pronounced Dadaojia lingjie through the spiritual medium's mouth was Zhang Lu's spirit.

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Yes

Notes: "The spirit" is directed at the problems of the Daoist church, such as libationers' promotion.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– I don't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region

– Yes

Notes: In the text, "the spirit" praised the governance of the Wei kingdom.

- ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
 - Notes: That is probably why "the spirit" knew what happened in the Daoist church of this world, like, some libationers promoted themselves without obtaining the Celestial Master's recognition.

- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes

- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - I don't know

- ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
 - I don't know

- ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - I don't know

- ↳ Have other knowledge of this world
 - Specify: I do not know.

- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes

 - ↳ Human spirits can reward
 - Yes

 - ↳ Human spirits can punish
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - I don't know

- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– No

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life

– No

↳ In dreams

– No

↳ In trance possession

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists

– I don't know

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Communicate through other means

–Specify: No.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Notes: The text mentions "deities and transcendents" 神仙 and "transcendents" 仙人 but these sorts of beings are not present in the text.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

Notes: Yes, Dadaojia lingjie advocates some prevalent Confucian virtues, like "fathers are magnanimous and sons filial, husbands faithful and wives chaste, elder brothers respectful and the younger obedient." 父慈子孝，夫信婦貞，兄敬弟順 and "Pity the poor and cherish the old" 憐貧愛老.

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings care about whether libationers well managed their parishes and whether they fruitfully guided the faithful.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Specify: Supernatural beings care about whether religious specialists followed the rules of promotions set up by Celestial Masters.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, it says that if someone claims that there is no benefit of following the Dao, then the person has "three thousand of transgressions" (youzui sanqian 有罪三千). Here three thousand could mean depriving of the person's lifespan. In Daoism, the heavenly overseers can reduce one's lifespan by one hundred-day units (suan 算) or twelve-year units (ji 紀). So, the number three thousand might refer to reducing lifespan.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

Notes: In the text, "documents of the Three Offices" 三官文書 was spoken about. Three offices are heavenly overseers, referring to celestial officials (tianguan 天官), earth officials (diguan 地官) and water officials (shuiguan 水官). Therefore, the punishments

are possibly done by these heavenly officials.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

Notes: It was done to re-establish the rules concerning promotions in the Daoist church and to rectify incorrect practices.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

Notes: Although the text itself does not mention any specific rituals that should be followed by practitioners, the purpose of the composition of the text is to rectify the aberrant practices and to guide practitioners to come back to the "right" practices, so it is supposed to enforce ritual-devotional adherence.

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, for those following the guidelines, they would be selected as seed people 種民 of latter-day generation, avoiding disasters and enjoying eternal peace. In other words, being not selected is a kind of punishment.

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group

– Yes

↳ Punishments in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure

– I don't know

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure?

– I don't know

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form?

– I don't know

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm?

– Yes

↳ Other form of punishment

– Specify: No.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

Notes: The text says that the people who observed the rules would "have no disasters and illnesses" 消災無病. Conversely, those who did not abide by the rules would encounter disasters and have illnesses in this world.

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– Yes

↳ Political failure?

– No

↳ Defeat in battle?

– No

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– No

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– No

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– No

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– No

↳ Sickness or illness?

– Yes

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– No

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: No.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, it says that "[People who follow the guidelines will] encounter no disasters and have no illnesses, and will become the seed people of latter-day generation." 災消無病，得為後世種民.

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
 - No
- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence
 - No
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms?
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
 - No
- ↳ Done randomly
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?
 - Yes

Notes: It says that the people who follow the guidelines will become the "seed people" 種民 of the latter-day generation.

- ↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Consists of eternal happiness?
 - Yes
- ↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?
 - Yes

↳ Other?

– Yes

Notes: The "seed-people" are promised to survive the cataclysms at the end of the world. In addition, a new and unblemished society will start afterward. According to Eastern Jin (317-420) scripture, "Annals of Latter-Day Saint" 上清後聖道君列紀, the lord of Golden Portal was to come forth in a year marked by the cyclical signs renchen 壬辰 from mount Qingcheng 青城 to establish a new world inhabited by the chosen or seed-people of the Dao.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, it says that people will "encounter no disasters and have no illnesses" (xiaozai wubing 消災無病).

↳ Highly emphasized?

– Yes

↳ Consists of good luck?

– Yes

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– No

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– No

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?

– Yes

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– No

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?
 - No
- ↳ Other?
 - Specify: No.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

- No

↳ At specified time in future

- Yes

Notes: The eschaton can be calculated, even though our text does not mention it. According to another Celestial Masters' text, the Demon Statues of Lady Blue (nūqing guilü 女青鬼律) written around in the fourth century, the eschaton will happen in the year of Gengzi (gengzi zhinian 庚子之年) which is designated by the sexagenary cycle. While according to another text from another Daoist tradition, Shangqing 上清 tradition, the Declarations of the Perfected (Zhen'gao 真誥), the eschaton will take place along the disasters of yang-nine, one-hundred-six (yangjiu bailiu 陽九百六) and the time of yang-nine, one-hundred-six can also be known by means of measuring the water levels in Yincheng 陰成 mountain and Yangchang 陽長 mountain. However, since the eschaton cannot be avoided, the ways to become seed people to survive are important. The ways include practicing good deeds and practice Daoist arts, like the arts of the bed-chamber and so forth.

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– No

↳ At some other time [specify]

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

↳ Divine judgment event

– No

↳ Restoration of the world

– Yes

Notes: After the eschaton, the world will be restored. According to the Demon Statues of Lady Blue, Lord of Transcendence of Great Peace (Taiping shenxian jun 太平神仙君) will appear and rule the new world, while in the Shangqing text, the Declarations of the Perfected, the new world will start from the year of Renchen (Renchen zhisui 壬辰之歲) and be ruled by Latter Sage Thearch Lord of the Golden Pylons (Jinque housheng dijun 金闕後聖帝君).

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

– Yes

↳ Establishment of new political system

– I don't know

↳ Establishment of new religious system

– I don't know

↳ Other form of eschatology?

– Specify: There are some other kalpas (jie 劫) in Daoist tradition: Longhan 龍漢, Yankang 延康, Chiming 赤明, Kaihuang 開皇, Shanghuang 上皇.

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive

– No

↳ A subset of the religion in-group members will survive

– Yes

Notes: A group of selected people (zhongmin 種民) called seed people will survive.

↳ All members of the sample region will survive

– No

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton

– No

↳ Other survival condition [specify]

–Specify: No.

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text advocates Confucian virtues. For instance, "I have circulated day and night, traveling around within the four seas and journeying beyond the eight extremities, all from the desire to cause the ruler to be humane and his ministers loyal, father magnanimous and sons filial, husbands faithful and wives chaste, elder brothers respectful and the younger obedient—in short, to bring peace to all below Heaven." 吾晨夜周流四海之內，行於八極之外，欲令君仁，臣忠，父慈，子孝，夫信，婦貞，兄敬，弟順，天下安靜. Translation please see: Stephen R. Bokenkamp, *Early Daoist Scripture* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1997), 174.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

- ↳ Courage (generic)
 - No
- ↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence
 - Yes
- ↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
 - Yes
- ↳ Generosity/charity
 - Yes
- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
 - No
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
 - No
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation
 - No
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - No

- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - No
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - No
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - No
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
 - No
- ↳ Optimism/hope
 - No
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
 - No
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
 - Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding
– No

↳ Discernment/intelligence
– No

↳ Beauty/attractiveness
– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
– Yes

↳ Other important virtues
– Yes

Notes: Wives should be chaste; younger brothers should be obedient; ministers should be loyal to the king.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?
– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?
– No

Does the text require castration?
– No

Does the text require fasting?
– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?
– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the text states "if you are able to act in accordance with the essential teachings--so that ministers are loyal, children filial, husbands trustworthy, wives chaste, elder brothers respectful, younger brothers obedient--and you are not inwardly of two hearts, then all may go well for you and you may achieve the status of seed people." 能如要言，臣忠子孝，夫信婦貞，兄敬弟順，內無二心，便可為善，得種民矣. Translation from Bokenkamp's *Early Daoist Scriptures*, 177.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A state

Notes: The Celestial Master community is a theocratic state. Based on the received literature, we are told that it was Zhang Ling 張陵 (34-156) who founded the Celestial Masters upon a Covenant with the Powers that was both correct and unique in the world (Zhengyi mengwei 正一盟威) in Sichuan 四川 region in the first year of Han'an 漢安 reign period (142CE). After Ling died, this Celestial Masters movement was continued by Ling's son Zhang Heng 張衡 (?-179) and grandson Zhang Lu 張魯 (? -215). This text has been attributed to either Zhang Ling or Zhang Lu. They have been regarded as the first, second, and third Celestial Master respectively. Under the Celestial Masters, there were twenty-four parishes established and twenty-four libationers were set up to govern twenty-four parishes. The elections of libationers were decided by the "true pneuma".

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A state

Notes: Compared to early Daoist texts, such as Laozi xiang'er zhu 老子想爾註 attributed to Zhang Lu as well, Dadaojia lingjie ostensibly praised Confucian virtues and the ruling of the Wei kingdom, so the composition of Dadaojia lingjie apparently was influenced by the authority and the reproduction of the text, if it once widely circulated in the Daoist church, was certainly influenced by the authority too.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: I do not know.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– Yes

Notes: The text states that the constant chaos was caused by the kings and people's losing faith in the dao. If they all followed and attended the dao, the world should have been harmonious in an ideal order, in which the king was benevolent; the ministers were loyal; the husbands were trustworthy and wives were chaste. It is a world without famine, poverty, and wars. So, the text addresses the populace's welfare as a whole.

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– I don't know

Notes: We know little about the organization of the Celestial Masters after they were moved to the North. The system of twenty-four parishes declined, so it is not sure that whether the text would be studied in any formal Daoist educational institutions.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Notes: The text was primarily directed at libationers' transgressions.

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– I don't know

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy permanently?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the text criticizes those libationers who since the fifth year of Grand Harmony 太和 reign period (231CE), did not conform to old rules that stipulated that the selection and promotion of libationers "emanated" from the Celestial Master's pneumas. In other words, the Celestial Master was higher than libationers of twenty-four parishes and it was the Celestial Master who decided who would be libationers.

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy temporarily/seasonally?

– No

↳ Does the text dictate how the group's adherent's interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group?

– No

Notes: The text does not directly dictate how followers should interact with the official bureaucracy of the Wei, but the text claims that "from today, I will hide from the world. I entrust you to the Wei" 從今吾避世，以汝付魏 which seems to suggest that followers should obey orders given by the Wei rulers just like how they listened to the Celestial Masters.

↳ Does the text dictate how individuals interact with other institutional bureaucracies?
– No

↳ Does the text regulate the primary supporting income of the place?
– No

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out land?
– No

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out tools?
– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?
– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?
– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?
– Yes

Notes: It mentions that in the end of the Eastern Han 東漢 (25-220), the world suffered from wars including the Yellow Turban Rebellion (huangjin qiyi 黃巾起義) led by Zhang Jiao 張角 (? -184). It was Cao Cao 曹操 who ended the warfare and unified the northern region.

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?
– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?
– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the text celebrates the victory and the protection of the Wei military force led by Cao Cao 曹操. It was Cao Cao, the Martial Thearch 武帝 who launched the empire. Even though a number of people died during the wars, their descendants would no longer suffer injury.

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

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